

Tartrate Complex of Copper

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R. N. Sensarma¹ has determined the instability constant of copper tartrate complex by conductivity method as 6.1×10^{-3} . Shin Suzuki² has found the complexity constant of the complex as 9.32×10^{-4} by E.M.F. method. In the present paper, copper tartrate complex has been studied by pH measurement method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Experiment I: The curve A represents the results of pH titration of 200 ml. of a solution containing 0.0025 g.mol of tartaric acid and curve B that of the same volume of another solution containing 0.0025 g.mol. of tartaric acid and 0.0020 g.mol. of copper sulphate against $N/2$ sodium hydroxide at 30°.

Experiment II: 150 ml. of a solution containing 0.0010136 g. mol. of copper sulphate is titrated against 1.023 $M/10$ sodium tartrate at 30°.

Experiment III: 150 ml. of a solution containing 0.0105 g.mol. of sodium tartrate is titrated against 1.04 M copper sulphate at 30°.

The reactions taking place in the experiment I may be represented by the equation (1)

The number (n) of protons liberated per atom of copper had been calculated according to the method followed in the investigation of citrate, tartrate and malate complexes of iron³.

The value of n increases gradually and is more than 2 above pH 4.0. Assuming n to be 2 below pH 4.0, the equilibrium constant of the reaction (1) is calculated and is recorded in Table 1. The mean value of K is found to be 2.62×10^{-3} .

Above pH 4.0, n is greater than 2. The formation of the neutral complex is complete and it dissociates to an anionic complex C_1^- according to the reaction 2.

The equilibrium constant of the reaction is represented by the equation (2-1)

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}]} \quad \dots (2-1)$$

1. R. K. Patnaik and S. Pani, *This Journal*, 1950, 683.
2. (Science Repts. Research Inst. Tohoku Univ. Ser. 1952, A₃, 292-6).
3. H. K. Das, G. Mohapatra, R. K. Patnaik and S. Pani, Proceedings of the Symposium on the Chemistry of Coordination Compound, 1959, Part III, pp. 102-126.

The value of K_1 calculated as in the case of the citrate complex of cadmium⁴ is recorded in Table 1. The mean value of K_1 is 1.5×10^{-5} .

TABLE 1

pH	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^2$	$(-\Delta[\text{T}]) \times 10^4$	$[\text{CuSO}_4] \times 10^3$	a/b	n	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Cu}^{++}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{H}_2\text{T}] \times 10^3$	K $\times 10^3$	$K_1 \times 10^5$
2.9	1.904	2.90	9.69	0.5044	1.6484	7.411	2.279	2.451	2.11	
3.0	1.110	2.90	9.661	0.5753	1.7403	7.902	1.759	1.921	2.34	
3.2	1.076	3.00	9.614	0.7241	1.8651	8.598	0.987	1.165	2.97	
3.4	0.958	2.70	9.585	0.8770	1.901	8.742	0.828	0.7635	2.19	
3.8	0.730	2.10	9.541	1.184	1.9752	9.251	0.272	0.2436	3.51	
4.4	0.548	1.40	9.477	1.613	2.2153					1.09
4.6	0.587	1.60	9.443	1.722	2.3729					1.49
4.8	0.626	1.60	9.412	1.808	2.5038					1.61
5.0	0.684	2.00	9.376	1.872	2.6413					1.78

At pH 5.5, the solution turns turbid leading to the precipitation of copper tartrate. This compound dissolves in large excess of sodium hydroxide at higher pH.

In the experiment II, the reaction is represented by the equation (3) in the beginning and the equilibrium constant by the equation (3-1)

$$K_3 = \frac{[\text{C}_1^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Cu}^{++}][\text{T}^{--}]} \quad \dots (3-1)$$

Proton liberated due to the reaction is removed by C_1^- as a result of which neutral complex C is formed

Both the reactions will have the same effect. Above the 1 : 1 equivalence point the complex C dissociates to C_1^- and H^+ . Hence it can be shown that

$$[T] - [CuSO_4] = Z[HT^-] \quad \dots (4)$$

and

$$[C_1^-] = [H^+] + r[HT^-] \quad \dots (5)$$

where $Z = 1 + \frac{k_2}{[H^+]} + \frac{[H^+]}{k_1}$ and $r = 1 + 2 \frac{[H^+]}{k_1}$

The values of K_1 at different pH values were calculated according to the method followed in the cobalt citrate complex⁵ and is recorded in the Table 2. The mean value of K_1 is 1.12×10^{-5} which is in agreement with the results obtained in the experiment I.

TABLE 2

pH	[T] $\times 10^3$	[CuSO ₄] $\times 10^3$	Z	r	[HT ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^3$	[C] $\times 10^3$	K ₁ $\times 10^5$
4.3	8.445	6.20	2.4185	1.0911	0.9285	1.063	5.137	1.04
4.4	9.436	6.134	2.7692	1.0724	1.192	1.317	4.817	1.08
4.5	10.88	6.036	3.2107	1.0515	1.508	1.624	4.412	1.16
4.6	13.08	5.895	3.7698	1.0456	1.907	2.019	3.876	1.31

Below the 1 : 1 equivalence point it can be shown that

$$[T] = p[HT^-] + q[C_1^-] \quad \dots (6)$$

$$[T] = [HT^-](p + qr) + q[H^+] \quad \dots (7)$$

where $p = 1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_1} + \frac{k_2}{[H^+]}$ and $q = 1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_1}$.

The values of K_3 are calculated as done in the cobalt citrate complex and are tabulated in the Table 3. The mean value is 8.15×10^{-2} .

TABLE 3

pH	[T] $\times 10^3$	[CuSO ₄] $\times 10^3$	p	r	q	[HT ⁻] $\times 10^4$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^4$	[C] $\times 10^3$	[Cu ⁺⁺] $\times 10^3$	[T ⁻⁻] $\times 10^4$	K ₃ $\times 10^2$
4.02	4.458	6.459	1.8092	1.1736	7.409	3.569	5.145	3.298	2.647	2.578	7.21
4.04	5.180	6.416	1.8385	1.1658	7.120	4.469	6.123	3.748	2.056	3.381	8.04
4.06	5.790	6.377	1.8713	1.1584	6.845	5.302	7.009	4.098	1.579	4.200	9.21

In the experiment III, the reaction is represented by the equation (5). The formation of C_1^- has been assumed since the pH is above 4.0 where the neutral complex dissociates to C_1^- (Table 1). When the pH decreases considerably a major portion of the proton liberated, is removed by the reaction with C_1^- forming a neutral complex C.

The values of K_1 were calculated according to the method adopted in the experiment II and are tabulated in the Table 4. The mean value is 2.45×10^{-5} which is exactly similar to those obtained in experiments I and II.

It can be shown that $\frac{K_3 k_1 k_2}{K_1} = K$. The mean values of $\frac{K_3 k_1 k_2}{K_1}$ and K are 0.4152×10^{-3} and 2.62×10^{-3} respectively. The values are nearly same.

TABLE 4

pH	[T] $\times 10^2$	[CuSO ₄] $\times 10^2$	Z	r	[HT ⁻] $\times 10^2$	[C ₁ ⁻] $\times 10^2$	[C] $\times 10^3$	K ₁ $\times 10^5$
4.3	6.372	4.004	2.4185	1.0911	0.9795	1.074	2.93	1.84
4.4	6.775	3.359	2.7692	1.0724	1.234	1.328	2.031	2.61
4.5	6.805	2.867	3.2107	1.0575	1.227	1.299	1.568	2.62
4.6	6.841	2.374	3.7698	1.04566	1.185	1.242	1.132	2.75

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